

The structure of the imidophosphoranes was further confirmed by hydrolysis. When compounds (I) were refluxed with dilute HCl for three hours, gave the parent aminooxadiazole hydrochloride and triphenylphosphine oxide, identified by mixed m.p. and comparison of the i.r. with an authentic.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Beckman IR-5A unit. All melting points are uncorrected.

The key starting 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were obtained by oxidative cyclisation of aldehyde semicarbazones¹⁰.

N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)triphenylimidophosphoranes(I) :

A well stirred suspension of dibromotriphenylphosphorane (1 m.mol) in 30 ml dry benzene was treated slowly (30 min) with a solution of aminooxadiazole (1 m.mol) and triethylamine (1 m.mol) in 30 ml dry benzene. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hr and then refluxed for four hrs. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was removed by filtration. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue crystallised from benzene.

Table I represents the physical and analytical data of (I).

TABLE I—TRIPHENYLIMIDOPHOSPHORANES(I)

No.	R	m.p. °C	Formula	Microanalysis	
				Calcd. %N	Found
Ia	H	170-172	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ OP	9.97	9.85
Ib	<i>m</i> -Cl	188-190	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OP	9.22	9.14
Ic	<i>p</i> -Cl	207-208	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OP	9.22	9.32
Id	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	176-178	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ OP	9.65	9.53
Ie	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	200-201	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ P	9.31	9.18

§ The composition of Ia and Ie was also checked by analysis for phosphorus.

Ia, Calcd. P, 7.36 Found 7.50.

Ie, Calcd. P, 6.87 Found 7.00

Hydrolysis of *N*-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)triphenylimidophosphoranes(I) :

Imidophosphoranes(I) (1 gm) was refluxed for three hours with dilute HCl (30 ml), then cooled and extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was washed with water and dried over sodium sulfate. Upon evaporation of benzene, triphenylphosphine oxide was obtained (70%), identified by mixed m.p. and comparison of the infrared with an authentic.

The parent aminooxadiazoles were obtained from the acidic solution by neutralisation with sodium hydroxide.

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Stereochemistry and Anti-inflammatory Activity of Carboxymethoximes of Ketones†

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DURING the course of an investigation of carboxymethoximes as anti-inflammatory agents, Dijk and Zwagemakers¹ reported the anti-inflammatory activity of a number of oxime ether derivatives. The observations concerning the stereochemistry and the anti-inflammatory activity of carboxymethoximes of ketones made in this laboratory are recorded in this communication.

Reaction of the oximes of various ketones with monochloroacetic acid in presence of sodium hydroxide in aqueous alcohol yielded the *o*-alkylated derivative as was evident from the fact that identical compounds were also obtained when the ketones were reacted with 2-(aminooxy)acetic acid hemihydrochloride (Fig. 1). The assignment of the

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NOTES

TABLE I—PMR AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF VARIOUS CARBOXYMETHOXIMES

Compd. No.	m.p. (°C)	Diagnostic PMR Data (ppm)	Molecular formula	Elemental analysis (%)	
				Required	Found
1	2	3	4	5	6
1E	136-7	CDCl ₃ , 3.66, 3.72 and 3.78 (3S, 3 × OCH ₃), 1E + 11.1 mg Eu(fod) ₃ , 3.69, 3.72 and 3.78 (3S, 3 × OCH ₃)	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NO ₄	C 66.89 H 5.96 N 4.87	66.72 5.84 4.91
1Z	115-7	CDCl ₃ , 3.53 (S, 2-OCH ₃), 3.73 (S, 2 × OCH ₃), 1Z + 10.5 mg Eu(fod) ₃ , 3.75 and 3.76 (2S, 2 × OCH ₃), 3.88 (S, 2-OCH ₃)	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NO ₄	C 66.89 H 5.96 N 4.87	67.20 6.04 4.68
2E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 3.63, 3.71 and 3.76 (3S, 3 × OCH ₃), 4.46 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ NO ₆	C 61.60 H 5.55 N 4.06	62.36 5.78 4.16
3E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 3.59 and 3.72 (2S, 2 × OCH ₃), 4.38 and 4.44 (broad d, -OCH ₂ CH=CH ₂ and N-OCH ₃ resp), 5.08-5.37 (m, OCH ₂ CH=CH ₂), 5.72-6.08 (m, OCH ₂ -CH=CH ₂)	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ NO ₆	C 64.68 H 5.70 N 3.77	64.82 5.47 4.06
4E	84-5	CCl ₄ , 2.28 (S, CH ₃), 3.59 (S, OCH ₃) and 4.47 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₄	C 68.22 H 5.72 N 4.68	68.47 5.95 4.56
5	104-5	CDCl ₃ , 3.44 and 3.68 (2S, 2 × CH ₃ Ph), 4.78 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO ₃	C 72.07 H 6.05 N 4.94	72.30 6.34 4.68
6Z	93-4	CDCl ₃ , 1.90 (m, Ph-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -), 2.80 (q, Ph-CH ₂ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -), 4.78 (S, N-OCH ₃) and 7.95 (q, Ha, J=9 and 2Hz)	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ NO ₃	C 65.74 H 5.98 N 6.39	66.10 6.24 6.15
7E	78-80	CDCl ₃ , 1.80 (S, -C-CH ₃), 3.42 (S, Ph-CH ₃) and 4.65 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ ClNO ₃	C 54.66 H 5.00 N 5.79	54.95 4.70 5.91
8E	118-20	CCl ₄ , 1.70 (S, C-CH ₃), 2.77 and 2.90 (2d, one methylene proton), 3.18-3.64 (two sets of multiplets, Ph-CH- and one methylene proton) and 4.50 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ClNO ₃	C 65.16 H 5.46 N 4.22	65.31 5.67 4.35
9E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 0.72 (t, CH ₂ -CH ₃), 1.63-3.67 (m, showing CH ₂ CH ₃ , -CHCH ₂ Ph, PhCH-C=N-) and 4.55 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₃	C 73.29 H 6.80 N 4.50	73.52 7.12 4.44
10E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 0.83 (t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.90 (q, CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.23 (S, CH ₃), 2.68-2.84 (2d, one methylene proton), 3.1-3.6 (two sets of m, Ph-CH and one methylene proton) and 4.50 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ NO ₃	C 73.82 H 7.12 N 4.30	73.94 7.50 4.50
11E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 0.70 (t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.63-3.33 (m, CH ₂ CH ₃ , PhCH ₂ -CH- and Ph-CH-C=N-), 3.57 and 3.62 (2S, 2 × OCH ₃), 4.53 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₃	C 67.91 H 6.78 N 3.77	68.24 7.12 3.60
12E	72-74	CCl ₄ , 1.70 (S, C-CH ₃), 2.24 (S, CH ₃), 2.75 and 2.90 (2d, one methylene proton), 3.15-3.64 (two sets of multiplets, Ph-CH and one methylene proton) and 4.50 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₃	C 73.29 H 6.80 N 4.50	73.35 6.59 4.49
13E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 1.73 (S, C-CH ₃), 2.85 and 3.0 (2d, one methylene proton) 3.33-3.80 (two sets of multiplets Ph-CH and one methylene proton) and 4.50 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ ClNO ₃	C 65.16 H 5.46 N 4.22	65.50 5.75 4.23
14E	Oil	CCl ₄ , 0.85 (t, CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.50-2.35 [m, Ph-CH-(CH ₂) ₂ -Ph], 2.55 (q, CH ₂ CH ₃), 3.35 (t, Ph-CH-) and 4.47 (S, N-OCH ₃)	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ NO ₃	C 74.31 H 7.42 N 4.13	74.20 7.72 4.42

Fig. 1

stereochemistry of various carboxymethoximes was made on the basis of their PMR spectra. On the basis of the deshielding effect experienced by either alkyl or aromatic protons due to the magnetic anisotropic effect of -NOCH₂ group², the stereochemical assignment was made and are recorded in Table 1. Although Dijk and Zwagemakers¹ reported the predominant formation of the E-isomer of oxime and oxime-ethers of a large number of phenyl ketones, even than the PMR spectra of the E and Z-isomers of **1** were studied in presence of the Eu(fod)₃ as the shift reagent. The two isomers of **1** were separated by column chromatography of the isomeric mixture of the oxime (E : Z : 8 : 1) which was prepared by conventional method. The predominant E-isomer failed to exhibit any deshielding effect of the methoxy signal at position-2 (2 Hz), while in the Z-isomer this methoxy signal showed a considerable shift (21 Hz) in the presence of Eu(fod)₃. The stereochemical assignment of **6** was made on the basis of the chemical shift of the aromatic protons which were shown by Buchler³ earlier to be of diagnostic value for stereochemical assignment. The stereochemistry of **7** was ascertained on the basis of comparative PMR studies with **5**. The two different chemical shifts of the two benzylic methylene protons in **5** indicated the magnetic anisotropic effect of the -N-OCH₂ group. Since the benzylic -CH₂ in **7** appeared at 3.42 δ, the E-configuration of the compound became evident. The configuration of **8-14** was studied on the basis of the chemical shift of -NOCH₂CO₂H protons. In carboxymethoxime of *p*-chloroacetophenone, the E-configuration of which was proved by X-ray crystallographic studies¹, the

-OCH₂CO₂H protons appeared at 4.58δ. On the other hand, the chemical shift of the same -NOCH₂CO₂H protons in **5** and **6** appeared at 4.78δ which indicated that in the E-configuration the alkyl group had a shielding influence on the -NOCH₂CO₂H protons. Since the latter protons in **8-14** appeared at around 4.5δ, the E-configuration of these compounds became obvious.

Besides the configurational problem the carboxymethoximes possess a conformational problem also, as would be evident from the fact that the carboxymethoxime of *p*-chloroacetophenone in the solid state exists in a conformation in which the oxime ether function lies in a plane making an angle of 25° with the phenyl ring and the carboxyl function is almost perpendicular to the oxime ether grouping¹. In the gaseous phase the conformation of the same compound allows the carboxyl group to be directed towards the N-atom. It would, therefore, be logical to expect that a complex carboxymethoxime like **8**, would possibly exist in different conformations in solution. The PMR spectra of **8**, the purity of which was meticulously checked by high pressure liquid chromatography, at 300 MHz exhibited two signals for -CH₂ and -NOCH₂ protons at δ 1.77, 1.78 and 4.69, 4.70 respectively. Since, such a minor difference in chemical shift can only arise because of different conformations in solution, it became obvious that **8** in solution existed in more than one conformations.

Anti-inflammatory Activity :

All the compounds were tested in albino mice (18-22 g) for toxicity. The anti-inflammatory activity was also tested in mice (18-22 g) of either sex at 1/5th of LD₅₀ doses. Graded doses of the compound were administered intraperitoneally to groups of five mice in order to ascertain the acute toxicity. The animals were observed continuously for 2 hr and mortality was noted after 24 hr. The approximate LD₅₀ (ALD₅₀) was calculated from mortality observed in different groups. Anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated against carrageenin induced oedema in mice following the procedure of Srimal and Dhawan⁴. One hour after the oral feeding of the compound, carrageenin 1% solution was injected into the left paw of the animals. The effect of the compound was assessed 4 hr after the injection of the carrageenin. Percentage inhibition of carrageenin induced oedema exhibited by **3E**, **5** and **8** were 30, 44 and 28% respectively.

Experimental

General method of the alkylation of oximes : A mixture of the appropriate oxime (0.01 mol), monochloroacetic acid (0.013 mol) and NaOH (0.03 mol) in aqueous alcohol (25 ml) was refluxed for 18-20 hrs. After the completion of the reaction, the solvent was distilled off under vacuo and the

residue extracted with ethyl acetate to remove the unreacted starting oxime. The aqueous layer was made acidic with dil. aq. HCl to yield the desired carboxymethoximes (40-90%).

Reaction of ketones with 2-(aminoxy)acetic acid hemihydrochloride: A solution of appropriate ketone (0.01 mol), 2-(aminoxy)acetic acid hemihydrochloride (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.03 mol) in ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed for 18-20 hrs. The solvent was removed under vacuo, and the residue extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to yield the desired carboxymethoximes (40-90%).

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Flavonoids of *Ipomoea dissecta*

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*IPOMOEA dissecta*¹ Willd. [syn. *I. optica* (L.) Roth.] belonging to the Convolvulaceae is reported to contain chlorogenic acid in the leaves². *I. fistulosa* has been recorded to contain kaempferol in the flowers³ and β -sitosterol in the leaves⁴. We now report the chemical components of the flowers of *I. dissecta*.

Fresh flowers (75 g) of *I. dissecta* collected from the Regional Engineering College Campus, Tiruchirapalli during late winter were extracted with hot 80% EtOH under reflux and the combined extract concentrated *in vacuo* and the aqueous concentrate fractionated successively into petrol (60-80°), ether and ethylacetate (EtOAc) solubles. The petrol fraction did not yield any crystalline solid.

The residue (0.1 g) from the ether fraction on crystallisation from Me₂CO yielded a yellow solid

(0.06 g) m.p. 277-79°, tetraacetate, m.p. 185-87° and was identified as kaempferol by R_f, colour reactions, uv and direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The residue (0.05 g) from the EtOAc fraction was dissolved in methanol and was subjected to preparative PC (Whatman No. 3, 15% HOAc) and the methanolic eluate of the only band that separated had λ_{\max} (MeOH) 243 (sh), 251 (sh), 268, 323 (sh), 365 nm; $\Delta\lambda$ (NaOMe)+50 nm; $\Delta\lambda$ (AlCl₃) and $\Delta\lambda$ (AlCl₃/HCl)+59 nm; $\Delta\lambda$ (NaOAc) nil (band II) and $\Delta\lambda$ (NaOAc/H₃BO₃) nil and responded to all the reactions expected of a flavone glycoside. It could be hydrolysed easily with 7% H₂SO₄ (100°, 2 hr) to yield kaempferol and glucose in almost equal quantities. The glycoside could therefore be identified as kaempferol-7-glucoside by R_f and uv data and the identity confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

This appears to be the first record of isolation of kaempferol and its 7-glucoside from *I. dissecta*.

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Antibacterial and Antialgal Activity of N-Isonicotinylamido-N'-Aryl/Guanidines

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CERTAIN alkyl/aryl guanidines or diaryl guanidine derivatives of isonicotinic acid hydrazide have been prepared with a view to evaluating their antibacterial activity. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide has been reacted with aryl amidine chlorides¹ in chloroform solution of the respective arylcyanamide² to afford hydrochloride salts (I and II). The